

PECULIARITIES OF USING A COGNITIVE APPROACH IN SHAPING THE LEXICAL SKILLS OF B1 LEVEL STUDENTS

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Abstract: this article can define the peculiarities of using a cognitive approach in shaping the lexical skills of B1 level students. There are given many different ways for developing B1 learners vocabulary.

Key words: language teaching, communicating, task, vocabulary teaching, teaching B1 level learners.

A long period of time grammar was viewed as the main task in second language Teaching B1 level learners. Mastery of grammatical structures was the main goal in second language acquisition. The Grammar--Translation Method dominated second language Teaching B1 level learners. On the contrary, vocabulary Teaching B1 level learners and acquisition were of relatively minor importance. Vocabulary development was approached as some kind of auxiliary activity and, often through memorizing decontextualised word lists. The relatively minor importance attached to lexical knowledge and context was visible in the scant attention paid to it by second language researchers and teachers in the last decade. Vocabulary, which is the basic material of the language, is, of course, of crucial importance in expressing ideas and thoughts when communicating. The following statement about the relationship between grammar and vocabulary demonstrated by the British linguist Wilkins in 1976 argues that “[w]ithout grammar, there are few things we can express; while without vocabulary, there is nothing we can express.” Wilkins verifies the importance of vocabulary in communication. Insufficient vocabulary or vocabulary difficulties will result in communicational barriers or failures. Without the mediation of vocabulary, no amount of grammatical or other types of linguistic knowledge can be employed in second language communication or discourse. Since the 1960s, many new ideas and approaches to the study of vocabulary acquisition in a second language have emerged through many English linguists’ efforts and research. Among them, Communicative Language Teaching B1 level learners (CLT) pedagogy which originated from the changes in the British Situational Language Teaching B1 level learners approach dating from the late 1960s deserves to be mentioned. Stemming from the socio-cognitive perspective of the socio-linguistic theory, with an emphasis on meaning and communication, and a goal to develop learners’ communicative competence, CLT evolved as a prominent language Teaching B1 level learners

method and gradually replaced the previous Grammar-Translation Method. In the last twenty years.

There are various theoretical studies on exploring the types of vocabulary knowledge related to the familiarity with a word (Richards (1976); Nation (1990); Carter (1992), etc.) Richards (1976) made the first attempt to list the different types of knowledge that are necessary to fully know a word. He was more concerned with applicability to pedagogical practice than attempting to provide a systematic framework for describing or accounting the word knowledge (Meara, 1996). In the word knowledge 10 list, there is no attempt to distinguish productive vocabulary from receptive vocabulary. Elaborating on Richards' list, Nation developed a list of various types of vocabulary knowledge that one must possess both receptively and productively in order to have complete command of a word: 1. the spoken form of a word (R (receptive): What does the word sound like?/ P 15 (productive): How is the word pronounced?) 2. the written form of a word (R: What does the word look like?/P: How is the word written and spelled?) 3. the grammatical patterns of the word (R: In what patterns does the word occur?/ P: In what patterns must we use the word?) 4. the collocational behavior of the word (R: what words or types of words can be expected before or after the word?/P: What words or types of words must we use with this word?) 5. how frequent the word is (R: How common is the word?/P: How often should the word be used?) 6. the appropriateness of a word (R: Where should we expect to meet this word/ P: Where can this word be used?) 7. the conceptual meaning of a word (R: What does the word mean?/ P: what word should be used to express this meaning?)

Vocabulary Teaching B1 level learners and acquisition has assumed an important role since 1980s in second language Teaching B1 level learners. Communicative Language Teaching B1 level learners, as an eminent second language Teaching B1 level learners approach, lays emphasis on learning target language through communicative activities. The study which aims to evaluate the effectiveness of Communicative Language Teaching B1 level learners in English vocabulary Teaching B1 level learners and learning in a comprehensive class in southern Sweden is a new trial to the writer indeed. Guided by the relevant theoretical background, the study which is composed of an English lesson's observation, a dictation and an interview demonstrates that compared with the traditional Grammar—Translation Method, Communicative Language Teaching B1 level learners based on many modern humanistic and communicative theories is effective in English vocabulary Teaching B1 level learners and learning in many aspects: 1) In the CLT classroom much vocabulary is not taught in the form of wordlist of isolated words any more, but taught in authentic contexts. Vocabulary Teaching B1 level learners focuses on developing communicative proficiency rather than commanding

the forms of the target language. 2) CLT makes learners acquire vocabulary knowledge naturally, rather than learning intentionally. Apart from it, the modified target language input which is gotten from conversational interactions between the teacher and learners enables them to get better understanding of vocabulary knowledge. 3) CLT promotes learners' communicative competence and stimulates their inner motivation since the communicative activities are close and relevant to their daily life. 4) CLT makes learners adopt the responsibility to their own learning and encourages them to discover the forms and structures of target language for themselves. 5) CLT prompts the development of learners' spirit of team cooperation by means of the communicative activities and cultivates learners' individuality by expressing their different views and ideas freely in the conversational interactions between them. Additionally, through the observation of the English lesson, the writer thinks that CLT makes great demands upon the professional skills and competence of teachers. CLT teachers need to have other abilities as well as the proficiency of target language, such as organizing ability, insight into learners. Therefore, it is recommended that second language teachers should enhance their standard in order to improve the effects in practical Teaching B1 level learners.

References:

- 1.Allen, V. F. (1983) Techniques in Teaching B1 level learners Vocabulary. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Berns, M. S. (1984) Contexts of Competence: Social and Cultural Consideration in Communicative Language Teaching B1 level learners. New York: Plenum Press.
- 2.Breen, M. & C. N. Candlin. (1980) The Essentials of a Communicative Curriculum in Language Teaching B1 level learners. Applied Linguistics. Brumfit, C. J.& K. Johnson. (1979) The Communicative Approach to Language Teaching B1 level learners. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Carter, R. (1992) Vocabulary, Cloze and Discourse. Harlow: Longman. Canale,
- 3.M.& M. Swain. (1980) Theoretical Bases of Communicative Approaches to Second Language Teaching B1 level learners and Testing. Applied Linguistics. Canale
- 4.M.& M. Swain. (1983) From Communicative Competence to Communicative Language Pedagogy. Richards,J.and Schmidt, R. (eds.) Language and Communication London: Longman.
- 5.Carter, R. (1992) Vocabulary: Applied Linguistic Perspectives. London: Routledge. Coady, J. (1987) Research on ESL/EFL Vocabulary Acquisition: Putting it in Context. New York: Oxford University Press.

